

”MY COAT OF ARMS –PRIDE”

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Annotation: this article discusses the state emblem of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the history of its creation, which is our pride. As I wrote the article, I had a lot of information about our coat of arms. In the process of covering the topic, I have published an image of our coat of Arms, created over the years .

Key words: cotton, wheat, chambered, star, crescent, silver, gold, sickle,hammer Sun, sketch .

The coat of arms (from German erbe-heritage) has long been considered a sign of meroism, which was used to distinguish between the own property of a family that owned certain estates or family dynasties that had one ancestor. For a long time, coats of arms served only as signs of personal authentication. They appeared in France in England in the XII century and for a century today spread to Western and Central Europe. During this period , Knights from different countries united as Crusaders were also tormented by such a problem as confusing their military or recognizing, misleading enemy fighters. The difference between the coat of arms and emblems is that it is made according to the rules of heraldry. For example, due to non-compliance with the rules of heraldry, the state symbols of Italy and France are not officially called a coat of arms, but a “symbol of the state”, and in the USA - “Great Seal of the United States”. In the East, among the Mongolian and Turkic peoples, family architectural symbols exist in the form of a stamp, which are given to each aristocratic surname. In Turkic peoples, including Uzbeks, the stamp was also understood as a sign of common ancestry, seals placed on the property of ancestors, including cattle. As a rule, from a certain breed, the offspring received the stigma of the ancestor and added additional element to it and changed it. There are several assumptions of the origin of the word” stamp". According to its Turkish version, the coat of arms meant “seal”. During the Golden Horde, the term was widely used in Central Asia, Eastern Europe, the countries of the near and Middle East, the Caucasus and the Caucasus. Hence, in general terms, the word stamp can be used, but a symbol that can fully meet the requirements of the coat of arms.

Coat of arms of Uzbekistan. We also had coats of arms until the coat of arms approved in 1992. The first coat of arms of Uzbekistan, which was part of the Soviet state, was approved in 1925. The first coat of arms in our history was in the form of a circle. At its top is a star of white color, on the left is cotton wool, and on the right is bug;the doy spikes are depicted, which continued on all the coats of arms adopted after the tradition, hususan, also present on our current coat of arms. The background of the coat of arms was gilded. Since the Arabic alphabet was in force in the Uzbek SSR until 1929, there are words written with the letters arb at the top of the coat of arms. In the middle of the coat of arms are your tongues sickle and hammer;the symbols of A are depicted on the lower one, and on its back is the shining sun. In the lower part of the sickle and hammer symbols, the Uzssr script of the krill

Alphabet is placed. At the very bottom of the coat of arms is the inscription “workers of all countries, unite”.

On February 14, 1937, the new coat of arms of the Uzbek SSR will be adopted. In this coat of arms, its structure undergoes some changes. In particular, the coat of arms is reduced to a white background, The Shape of the cotton and wheat link changes, the inscriptions in the Arabic spelling change to those in the Latin spelling. The inscriptions “Unite the workers of all countries”, written in the lower part of the old coat of arms, are removed and put on a cotton tie in Russian, on a red ribbon in a wheat tie in the Uzbek language of the Latin alphabet “proletars of the whole world, unite! the words " come down. At the bottom of the sickle and hammer symbols, the inscription “Uzssr” in the krill Alphabet was changed to “UzSSR” in Latin letters.

The coat of arms of the Uzbek SSR, adopted in 1947, is practically no different from the previous one. Only the symbols of the Golden sickle and hammer, located in the center of the coat of arms, were changed to silver. In the writings, the words of the Latin alphabet were changed to words of the Krill Alphabet. The basis for this was the change of Alphabet in 1939 in the USSR to Krill in Latin.

In 1978, the last coat of arms of the Uzbek SSR was adopted. On this coat of arms, the sickle and hammer, which were first converted from gold to silver, were again transformed into a golden color. State emblem of the Republic of Uzbekistan In the first year of Independence, work began on the preparation of the state emblem, among other state symbols. Several variants of the new state coat of arms were proposed, but in the end the coat of arms drawing created by a group of artists and graphic masters of the art academia of Uzbekistan was approved. On July 2, 1992, the first president of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov signed the law “on the state emblem of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, which was registered with number 616-XII.

photo: one of the versions of the proposal for the coat of arms of the news service of the Uzbek Agency. Article 3 of the lawning describes the appearance of the coat of arms: “the state coat of arms of the Republic of Uzbekistan has the following appearance: mountains, rivers and a macro side consists of wheat spikes, and the right side is cotton sleds wrapped and opened in an attic consisting of cave Kings with sledges open, and the sun shines gilded rays over the Valley. At the top of the coat of arms, eight corners are depicted as a symbol of Republican heresy, on the inside of which a crescent moon and a star are depicted. In the center of the coat of arms is the symbol of happiness and erk love-the Humo bird, which wrote its wings. At the bottom of the coat of arms, the band of the chamber ribbon, which represents the state flag of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is written as “Uzbekistan”.

The draft law on the state emblem of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the resolution of the Supreme Council, the coat of arms are kept among the special valuable documents of the National Archives of Uzbekistan.

After the Latin script of the Republic of Uzbekistan was given the status of the state language, a slight change was made to the coat of arms. At the bottom of the coat of arms, the word “Uzbekistan” in Cyrillic was written in the Latin alphabet “Uzbekistan” on the band of the chambar ribbon, which represents the state flag of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the left side, the drawing of a cotton flower on the chamfer was changed to an openwork cotton swab. The figure of a star was taken to the left by taking the shape of a crescent inside an eight-pointed star. The law”on the state emblem of the Republic of Uzbekistan ” establishes procedures for its use. According to the law, the image of the state emblem can be permanently installed: in the buildings of the residence of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, bodies of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Also, the image of the coat of arms can be used in monetary signs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, passports of the Fukuro of the Republic of Uzbekistan and diplomatic passports issued to the Fukuro of the Republic of Uzbekistan, border columns installed on the state borders of the Republic of Uzbekistan, postal wagons and mailboxes of the national operator of the Elements of the state emblem are not allowed to be included in the details or promotional materials of documents of non-governmental organizations. Signs with the image of the state emblem cannot be used for commercial purposes for the transfer of goods(works, services) that are being produced or are being realized. The symbols of non-commercial organizations cannot be similar to the state emblem. The repeated image of the state emblem, regardless of its large size, must clearly correspond to the color and black and white image to which this law is attached. Above, we wrote that the coat of arms was not approved by a drawing created by a group of artists and Countess of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan. In this group, the main tasks are performed by the graphist-artist Anvar Mamajonov. However, information about this is rare. Anvar Mamajonov was born in 1950 in the city of Tashkent. From 1968 to 1973 he studied at the National Institute of painting and design. Artists of his time E. Liepene and B. Shupak studied the secrets of skill in his workshops. During his career, Alisher Navoi, Pirimkul Kadyrov, Muhammad Ali, Azim Suyun, HUrshid Davron, Yamin Kurban, Muhtor Khudaykulov worked on his works, as well as illustrations for folk epics and Efendi anecdotes. Shahsi exhibitions were held in countries such as the USA, Bahrain, Belgium, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia, India. Participant and winner of more than twenty international exhibitions.

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